

Challenges and Reforms in Higher Education: A Critical Analysis of K. L. Kamal's *Campus: A Novel*

Prof. Dr. Bhupendra N. Kesur

Professor and Head,

P. G. Department of English,

M. J. College, Jalgaon (MS)

Email: bnkesur@gmail.com

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5613-2198>

Rahul S. Wankhede

Research Student

M. J. College, Jalgaon (MS)

Email: rahulwan2812@gmail.com

Abstract:

*This research paper explores the genre of the campus novel, focusing specifically on the Indian English novel *Campus: A Novel* by Prof. K. L. Kamal, published in 2002. The novel depicts the character of Chandrakant, a Vice-Chancellor, and his efforts to elevate his university despite facing significant political challenges. Indian English literature has seen a notable rise, especially in the portrayal of diverse aspects of life through novels. Among these, the campus novel has emerged as a significant trend, reflecting the complexities of university life in India. The postcolonial era has witnessed a flourishing of Indian novels, addressing a broad spectrum of themes including social, psychological, educational, political, and economic issues. This paper critically examines *Campus: A Novel*, delving into the educational system, the challenges facing higher education, the role of research, the impact of politics on education, and the role of universities in society, as depicted in this significant work of literature.*

Key Words: Campus Novel, Indian English Literature, Higher Education, Political Challenges.

Introduction:

The 21st century has become a powerhouse of knowledge, significantly transforming the educational, social, and cultural landscapes of nations, largely due to globalization. In *Globalization of Education: An Introduction*, Joel Spring (2014) discusses how globalization has brought about an interconnectedness that has profoundly influenced educational practices and policies worldwide. This interconnectedness has led to the widespread acceptance of principles such as freedom and equality, encouraging individuals to think beyond traditional frameworks.

Received: 22 July 2024

Revised: 13 August 2024

Accepted: 19 August 2024

Copyright ♥ authors 2024

316

DOI: [HTTPS://DOI.ORG/10.5281/ZENODO.13342322](https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.13342322)

The impact of education is now evident in various facets of life, including social, economic, cultural, and moral domains, underscoring its crucial role in national development.

In recent years, there has been a notable surge in Indian English novels, with literature encompassing every aspect of life. The postcolonial period, in particular, has seen Indian novels flourish, addressing a broad spectrum of themes such as social, psychological, educational, political, and economic issues. Among these, the campus novel has emerged as a significant genre, depicting the life within universities and colleges in India. Campus novels, also known as academic novels, provide a microcosm of university life, exploring political, social, economic, academic, and non-academic issues in a closed academic environment (Showalter, 2005). Stating about the trend of campus novel, it started first in European countries. “David Lodge is one of the most popular writers of this genre in Britain. Even before him the novels came like *Pinn* (1955) by Vladimir Nabokov. *Lucky Jim* (1954) by Kingsley Amis. However, David Lodge considers *The Groves of Academy* (1952) by Mary McCarthy, as the first classic campus novel. (Devi, 2017), These novels critically engage with the theme of academic reforms, as seen in works like K. L. Kamal's *Campus: A Novel*, Chetan Bhagat's *Five Point Someone*, and D. R. Sharma's *Miracles Happen*. Githa Hariharan's *In Times of Siege* also explores similar themes through a controversial, virtual history classroom that sparks liberal dissent.

In *Campus: A Novel*, published in 2002, Prof. K. L. Kamal presents the story of Chandrakant, a Vice-Chancellor, who grapples with the challenges of upgrading his university amidst political turmoil. Chandrakant is portrayed as an ambitious individual who strives to elevate his university to national prominence by fostering a research-based environment. However, he faces significant obstacles due to the dirty politics of some staff members. Despite these challenges, Chandrakant remains steadfast in his efforts, ultimately gaining the respect and understanding of those who initially opposed him. The novel contrasts the present-day scenario of universities with the past, highlighting the current lack of dedication, belongingness, and sense of duty. As Kamal (2002, p. 65), poignantly notes, universities, once revered as temples of learning, research, creativity, and culture, have now become centers of political activism and inflated egos, leading to a "directionless and motiveless" higher education system.

Discussion:

Educational system:

Education is a key factor in national development, creating well-cultured and civilized societies. A robust education system strengthens society socially, culturally, morally, politically, and economically. Education should be free from biases, promoting integrity and inclusiveness between administration and educators. Conflicts between administrators and teachers can lead to the collapse of the education system. Chandrakant realizes that some people derive satisfaction

Received: 22 July 2024

Revised: 13 August 2024

Accepted: 19 August 2024

Copyright ♥ authors 2024

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13342322>

from harming others, highlighting the lack of work ethics in the university. “There was no work ethics here in the university; the only morality that prevailed was one of the encroachments and a wish to show the other down.” (Kamal, 2002, p.16). His grandson observes no difference between the behavior of students and teachers, indicating the severity of the issues faced by the Vice-Chancellor. Chandrakant’s grandson said stammering, “Grandfather, I can see no difference between students and teachers. They too are speaking in such loud, angry voices like the students. Grandpa I come here rarely, but now I will not come at all. I cannot see you harassed like this, I really pity you!” (Kamal, 2002, p.35).

The novel suggests linking jobs with higher education to address problems of indiscipline and rebelliousness. Four-year Gudiya said “Grandpa Chhotu is right. I will ask my mother never to be the V.C., how dangerous it is to be a VC. (Kamal, 2002, p.35). This incident shows troubles in the life of the VC in the novel. When the group of some students marches towards the VC room, they shout and give some slogans against VC. Students are attached with some political parties. Chandrakant’s views about the students are that the students could still be motivated. Perhaps majority of the students could be inspired to study and they must have an aim in their life. “Only if jobs could be linked with higher education, the problems of indiscipline, rebelliousness and obstinacy would be solved. But here, where education, itself was purposeless and undirectional, cut off from the problems of society, inculcating merely egoism and feelings of self-esteem, such university education was indeed futile and could do no good in itself” (Kamal, 2002, p.38). The novel emphasizes the need for university education to provide job assurance and focus on societal needs, fostering a research environment for societal betterment.

The novel criticizes the lack of respect among teachers and their profession. It emphasizes the importance of teachers in inculcating societal values and protecting culture. The novel describes the tendency of teachers and professors towards their colleagues. “The tendency in the university has become so vitiated that there is no respect between teachers and no respect of the teachers for their profession. They can accept an IAS or an ex-army official as their Vice Chancellor, but not so one from among their fraternity. When this is the state of affairs in the teaching community, what can be said of the students? (Kamal, 2002, p.51). Teachers are very much important to inculcate the values in the society and protect the culture. As to state the importance of teachers Chanakya says that "where politicians, scientists and officers fail, teachers become the upholders and protectors of culture". (Kamal, 2002, p.62)

The novel focuses on true meaning of education. Students are the pillars of education system and they are pillars of new India. As the character Chandrakant says about the students and the thoughts of Mahatma Gandhi about education. He further says:

I want the students to believe in the dignity of labour, to Value things created by the hands as much as they value things created by the mind. Like Gandhiji, I too, believe that a carpenter's a plumber's, a barber's job is as important as a doctor's or a lawyer's. Gandhiji himself was a lawyer so he had a first- hand- knowledge about the nature of a lawyer's work. The philosophers think that in an educated and progressive society one can do away with the service of a lawyer and a doctor—it is possible that one may need the service of a doctor, but a lawyer's services should never be required. (Kamal, 2002, p.62)

The role of universities is so important to build the nation on the base of holistic development. He says that universities should not become only centres of excellence in science but there should be social and philosophic excellence. The universities of the third world should not only become centres of excellence in science, but also strong philosophic and social centres to curb the growing scourge of science. A beautiful sentence has been included in the preamble of the UNESCO: "Since wars originate in the minds of men, so it is in the minds that peace must be strongly reinstated" (Kamal, 2002, p.64). The universities play the fundamental role for sustainable development in education and social. The universities of the Third World should not only become strongholds of science and technology but also places where new awareness and people's revolutions are generated. Means though science and technology has become the important part of human life but humanitarian awareness peace is necessary in this third world.

Western work culture focuses on open communication and collaboration of flatter organizational structure. Because of this work culture they have been able to rule over three fourths of the world's resources and become so prosperous, educated, and powerful and reach the pinnacles of science and technology. Many developing countries, including India, are passing, through trying times; they are steeped deep in the quagmire of terrifying poverty, total dependence, demeaning illiteracy and suffocating ignorance. In the developed countries of the world, higher education has played a crucial role, their teachers, researchers, scientists are respected and have a decisive role in policy making. It is from there that the university, culture has evolved (Kamal, 2002, p.65). Everyone should have to get rid of the typecast mindset and accept realistic attitude, vital role of higher education to change the world for peace and harmony. Certain steps are needed for improvement of higher education system.

Highlighting the importance of Universities, Chandrakant says, Universities are not simply the institutions of bricks and stones but they are living institutions which impart knowledge and wisdom in the society and make the pupils to think rationally and logically. As the VC, Chandrakant asks the question to the other faculty members in the present novel:

Is a university merely an edifice of bricks, stones and mortar or is it a living institution with a pulsating soul? Every one of us has created a niche for ourselves, we like to work in our own labs, departments, offices, but our viewpoints are getting limited, narrowed, our way of thinking is not holistic and this is cause for worry. We always think as to what the university can give us, but the need is to think what we can contribute to the growth of the university. (Kamal, 2002, p.66)

Universities are the major institutions in the progress of the nation. There is the need to think about our contribution in the growth of the universities.

When one of the students of students' union, Padmini talks about the present education and employment she asks the question to the VC. She speaks that today's youth are impressed by the great national leaders of the Gandhian era. She says that they are indeed proud of the educationist and litterateurs. Next, she asks the question to the VC, Sir, what are we to do with their ideals? Can they feed us, clothe us, and give us jobs? What use is that education that cannot help us to quench our thirst and assuage the pangs of hunger? Perhaps you know, or maybe you do not, that graduates are forced to pull rickshaws, reduced to doing menial labor. We can understand all this if there is economic balance if there is not much difference between the rich and the poor, but such a scenario is terrifying! (Kamal, 2002, p.78). It is the harsh reality of education; it grew on quantity basis but not on quality basis. It is the production of qualified human resources. The present education system does not serve the purpose for which it has been initiated. Generally, education system has become a profit base business that quality is lost in the increase of quantity.

Politics in Education:

Education civilizes and installs ethical and moral values in individuals. However, political corruption in the education system is a daily problem. The novel addresses the demands of the Students' Union President, highlighting the politicization of universities and the resulting corruption

The President of the Students' Union gave the VC a charter of demands, of which the main were: Stop the politicizing of the university Not to stop the students from appearing in the examination because of shortage of attendance; Internal evaluation should be 50% of the total market There must be provision for bonus marks: There is a lot of corruption prevailing in the Secrecy Department therefore the names of the paper setter and examiner must be published in America the students know beforehand who sets a certain paper as it is influential people get to know of the paper setters somehow or the other (Kamal, 2002, p.21).

Politics has been interfering in the present education system. Mostly the view towards the education is profit making by increasing the quantity only. “Generally, education itself has become so profitable a business that quality is lost in the increase of quantity of professional institutions with quota system and politicization adding fuel to the fire of spoil system” (Giri, 2016). Policies and amendments are made, commissions are set up, but the reality at the ground level remains different. The novel critiques the blend of education and corruption, turning education into a profit-driven business, losing quality in the process. The people in government every time take a pledge to increase GDP on education, but the actual spending keeps hovering less than decided percentage. So, the policies and amendments are made, commissions are set up, but the reality is different on ground level. The blend of education and corruption makes it a more deadly combo. The motto of education system should only to provide education and knowledge but they are providing money to the businessman and politicians. They see it as an industry where money flows uninterrupted, irrespective of any recession. At such moments Chandrakant would also start to think about the disturbing influences of the outside world on the university. Were not the teachers, staff and students open to the goings-on of the society at large? Did the virtues and vices of the political leaders, politicians, government officials, businessmen and others not affect them? Were they ignorant of how the politicians and officers became millionaires overnight? This warning had, very early during Independence, been sounded by an eminent journalist, Durgadas, in his epoch-making book *From Curzon to Nehru and After*. He had cited this statement of a great industrialist: “Our ancestors had taught us not to meddle with politics while conducting our business, but if our business needs it, then we should not hesitate to buy out a king as well. Are the effects of politics and black money hidden from anyone? Everyone has seen the elite class breaking law and order to pieces” (Kamal, 2002, p.37).

Chandrakant reflects on the negative influence of the outside world on the university. Universities are the temples of learning, research and creativity, but due to unnecessary interference of politics in education these temples are broken somehow. As from the point of view of Chandrakant,

He felt that most of the Indian universities had ceased to be temples of learning, research, creativity and culture; instead they had become centers of political activism, inflated egoism, unbridled individualism and other non-academic pursuits. According to him, higher education had become directionless, motiveless and till such time as there would be no sense of belongingness there would be no change for the better. (Kamal, 2002, p.65)

According to him the university where one studied, where one worked, if it does not belong to him, if this feeling is not there, everything will come to an end. Chandrakant was often disturbed by the thought that he was not being able to do all that he wanted to for the improvement of the university. He thinks that “The consumer culture was at its peak on the university campus, ambitions were soaring to the skies. The forlorn books in the library only enhanced the beauty of

the showcases or were food for the worms” (Kamal, 2002, p.36). Once Chandrakant had been invited to preside over a Thinker's Forum where the Governor of UP, who was once a professor at BHU, was the Chief Guest. The Governor said in his keynote address: "The arrears that the teachers have received for their new fixation is more than several lakhs. Out of this amount received they have been able to replace their small cars with bigger ones, but the books in their libraries have not increased" (Kamal, 2002, p.36).

Talking about the today's teachers' work ethics Chandrakant opines that, "Today's teacher is not lagging behind in the race for new fashions, modern equipment and attractive home decor, but these sons and daughters of the Goddess Saraswati have all but forgotten their Mother's Temple! They are no longer role models for the students. Then whom should the students go to for inspiration?" (Kamal, 2002, p.36). He observes that the virtues and vices of political leaders, government officials, and businessmen affect the university community. The novel underscores the detrimental effects of political interference and black money on education, turning universities from temples of learning into centers of political activism and non-academic pursuits.

Research:

Teaching, research and public service these are the three missions of the modern university. *Campus: A Novel* highlights the need for renewed zeal and enthusiasm for higher education and research. The novel criticizes unqualified individuals who have risen to positions of authority through unethical means. Chandrakant speaks,

There were some, who had no right to be teachers at all, but still had reached the stage of being selected readers and professors. There were some who had forged certificates, mutilated their official records, did not take classes, used muscle power in altercations, and benefitted their relatives by straying from set procedures, plagiarized from published work for their own research and what not. (Kamal, 2002, p.55)

Universities and colleges play a vital role in shaping minds, advancing society through research. Researchers enhance thinking skills and acquire knowledge, contributing to societal welfare. The novel advocates for business firms to finance university laboratories, promoting joint ventures for societal benefit. The lack of respect for academicians is highlighted, emphasizing the need for universities to work for societal welfare.

I want business firms to finance the various laboratories of the University. This joint venture would help in the promotion entered into such joint ventures with business houses. I am deeply pained to note that society, too, never takes the

functioning of the university seriously. The academicians are not given their due respect. This respect can be earned when this centre for learning works for the welfare of the society. A UNESCO report has stated that India has 45% of the world's illiterates. The universities can wipe off this evil. But one must be determined and strong in one's endeavor if one wishes to combat illiteracy. (Kamal, 2002, p.62)

UNESCO's report on India's illiteracy rate underscores the importance of universities in combating illiteracy. As Kirti Matliwala (2016, p.4), in her research article 'Present Scenario of Higher Education in India'; states about the expenditure of research fund in India. As the higher education sector in India spends 4.1% of country's research fund. It is 17.0% in Germany; 22.6% in U.K. and 10.1% China. The research manpower in China is 8.6 lakhs; in India 1.3 lakhs and even in Korea it is 1.5 lakhs. Higher education scene in India should kindly be looked into.

The importance of autonomy in higher education is stressed, allowing universities to determine their duties and responsibilities. Autonomy grants teachers the freedom to study, teach, and research without hindrance. However, it does not permit unrestricted freedom or wishful behavior. Universities are crucial for future development, enabling the enlargement of knowledge horizons and innovative solutions through dedicated research. As Chandrakant speaks about the importance of autonomy in higher education:

The need for autonomy is a necessary condition because it is on the basis of this that a university can determine its own code of duties and responsibilities and follow them. Autonomy gives to the teacher's freedom to study, teach, and involve themselves in research and administration, unhindered. But of course, it does not allow for unrestricted freedom or wishful behavior. In a democratic society only those have a right to lead who are themselves enlightened and who are trustworthy and dedicated". (Kamal, 2002, p.67)

Due to number of reasons academicians are not able to give enough time for their research work. They are mostly busy in administrative work under the documentation necessity reason. As per the rule of UGC most of the institutes have no provision for research support schemes for faculties even if it exists on their policy papers.

Higher Education Challenges:

Higher education is directly related to national progress and betterment. The challenges faced by the world require enhancing excellence in education, a task for universities and educational institutions. Altbach, Philip G., Reisberg, Liz, and Rumbley, Laura E. (2009) state in a report on higher education, that is Trends in Global Higher Education: Tracking an Academic Revolution'

This report provides an overview of global trends and challenges in higher education, which can enhance the discussion on the need for reforms in higher education. As the novel *Campus* discusses about higher education, the quality of education must be reflected in students, teachers, administrators, and other staff.

Higher education is directly related to national progress and betterment. The challenges being faced by the world are indeed serious, but their resolution can be found in enhancing excellence in education and this in turn is the work of the universities and educational institutions of which students, teachers, administrators and other staff are integral parts. The quality of education an institution is imparting, must be reflected in all these parts of the said machinery. (Kamal, 2002, p.66)

Shrivastav, Shailaj Kumar (2016) in his research article ‘Need for Reconstruction of Higher Education System in India,’ delves the importance and quality of higher education:

Quality of education and training imparted in colleges and departments is also a matter of serious concern. Research and teaching are the two dominant aspects of any higher education system. Higher education should reflect the international, regional and national dimensions in both teaching and research. A good academic institution has to have an atmosphere where everyone is involved, engaged in doing new things, trying to find new things”.

Higher education should focus on quality and creativity for progress of individual and simultaneously for nation. Stating the true value of higher education for national development Hiwarkar Amruta, Nirbhavne Sushil and Rawat Poonam (2016) rightly explain in their research article ‘Higher Education in India: Present Status and Path Ahead’ the sustainability and superior value of higher education. “A value based higher education system empowers youth for self-sustainability by inculcating employment skills and hence reducing poverty”. The authors have explained in their article the critical aspects of delivering superior values and managing the higher education system in India.

Rabindranath Tagore's view that higher education harmonizes life with existence is cited, along with Ana Bali's (2014) statement on the four forces affecting higher education quality: changing university customs, increasing competition, rising costs, and impending crises. “Lee Harvey and Diana Green’s article 'Defining Quality' delves into the various dimensions of quality in higher education, providing a framework for understanding and improving educational standards” (Harvey and Green, 1993). As Ana Bali (2014) rightly states about the higher education scenario, “The quality of higher education is affected by the 4 Cs forces: i) The changing University

customs characteristics, ii) Increasing competition, iii) Rising costs, and iv) The impending crises”.

Reforms in higher education are necessary, requiring bottom-up changes from teacher-centered to learner-centered principles. These reforms must align with changes in university administration and system-level reforms. The Indian education system, one of the largest globally, faces myriad challenges, including funding shortages, curriculum development, quality assurance, accreditation, and policy planning. Investment in education is crucial for national progress. In a technology driven society, knowledge rewrites the fate of a nation and so does higher education. But the biggest challenge is obviously lack of enough investment in education sector.

Role of Universities in Society:

Universities are developed to meet the needs of the time, playing a vital role in societal change and development. They are centers for building the nation, generating, preserving, and transmitting knowledge. Universities have two main functions: enabling individuals to make a living and attain contentment and happiness. Most universities only partially fulfill the first function and overlook the second. Universities must bridge the gap between the educated elite and underprivileged groups. Kerr Clark (1963) mentions Newman’s views on role of universities in his book *The Uses of the University*. “A university training, said Newman, “Aims at raising the intellectual tone of society, at cultivating the public mind, at purifying the national taste, at supplying the true principles to popular enthusiasm and fixed aims to popular aspirations”. In *Campus: A Novel* Chandrakant opines regarding the role of university in the development of the society, “The society...expects the university to make such discoveries that will benefit those struggling between life and death, to bring brightness in the lives of those who have seen only darkness, who have never felt the freshness of spring and have only seen the wan woods of autumn”. (Kamal, 2002, p.25)

Conclusion:

This research paper examines the novel *Campus: A Novel* by Prof. K. L. Kamal, published in 2002. The novel depicts the challenges faced by Chandrakant, a Vice-Chancellor, as he strives to upgrade his university amidst significant political obstacles. Despite these challenges, Chandrakant remains hopeful and continues to work with genuine dedication. The paper provides a comprehensive overview of various aspects of the educational system, including higher education, the influence of politics on education, the role of universities, and the importance of research in higher education. The novel effectively captures the protagonist's ambitious vision for his university and his unwavering commitment to fostering a research-based atmosphere, even when confronted with the dirty politics of some of his staff members.

Received: 22 July 2024

Revised: 13 August 2024

Accepted: 19 August 2024

Copyright ♥ authors 2024

325

DOI: [HTTPS://DOI.ORG/10.5281/ZENODO.13342322](https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.13342322)

Chandrakant's journey underscores the critical role that leadership plays in navigating and overcoming institutional challenges. In summary, this research paper highlights the essential role of higher education in promoting the integrated development of individuals through intellectual, practical, and emotional growth. Higher education, as portrayed in the novel, is not just about acquiring knowledge but also about nurturing holistic development, which is vital for personal and societal progress.

References:

- Altbach, Philip G., Reisberg, Liz, and Rumbley, Laura E. (2009), *Trends in Global Higher Education: Tracking an Academic Revolution*. United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization, Paris.
- Bali, Ana. (2014), "Present Scenario of Higher Education in Indian System of Education: A Need to Improve Its Quality". *International Journal of Research (IJR)*, Volume-1, Issue-5, Page 69-84.
- Devi, U Gayatri. (2017), *Indian English Campus Fiction: A Study*. Authors Press, New Delhi. Print.
- Giri, Yogeshwari, L, and Virat V. Giri, (2016), "A Study on Indian Higher Education System". *International Journal in Management and Social Science*, Vol.04, Issue-07, p.749-761.
- Harvey, Lee, and Green, Diana. (1993), "Defining Quality." *Assessment & Evaluation in Higher Education*, vol. 18, no. 1, pp. 9-34.
- Hiwarkar, Amruta. and Sushil Nirbhavane, Poonam Rawat. (2016), "Higher Education in India: Present Status and Path Ahead". *International Journal in Management and Social Science*. Vol.04 Issue-06, p.442-456.
- Kamal, K.L. (2002), *Campus: A Novel*. University Book House LTD, Jaipur. Print.
- Kerr, Clerk. (1963), *The Uses of the University*, Harvard University Press, Cambridge. Print.
- Matliwala, Kirti. (2016), "Present Scenario of Higher Education in India, Journal of Youngish Teachers". *Interaction Forum.*, p.1-6.
- Showalter, Elaine. (2005), *Faculty Towers: The Academic Novel and Its Discontents*. University of Pennsylvania Press.
- Shrivastav, Shailaj Kumar. "Need For Reconstruction Of Higher Education System In India," *International Journal of Innovative Research and Advanced Studies (IJIRAS)*, Volume 3, Issue 9, August 2016, p. 239 – 245.
- Spring, Joel. (2014), *Globalization of Education: An Introduction*. Routledge, Print.